
LITERATURE REVIEW OF “DECORATIVE MOTIFS OF ISLAMIC CERAMICS IN STATE MUSEUM OF CULTURE HISTORY OF UZBEKISTAN IN SAMARKAND”

Hamdamova Shoir

Researcher

Introduction

This chapter will include a list of related references in concerns of answering all the research questions. It will also discuss in depth of Afrasiyab city in additional of the specific background of book about Culture History Museum of Uzbekistan in Samarkand. The motivational factors related to Islamic pottery will also be discussed along with the different research papers.

Ancient city Afrosiyob.

One example of the Central Asian civilization's lasting influence is Afrosiyob, a UNESCO World Heritage Site in Samarkand¹⁹, Uzbekistan. In the late 19th and early 20th centuries, research on Afrosiyob was mainly concerned with determining the city's chronological evolution and relationship to the old Sogdian civilization. Russian archaeologists such as V.A. Sarianidi and M.E. Masson created the foundation for comprehending the city's growth of material culture, its numerous cultural influences, and its urban layout with their groundbreaking works. Afrosiyob's significance as a hub for trade within the Silk Road network was further investigated by later studies, mostly conducted in the middle of the 20th century. Research conducted by A.A. Askarov, N.M. Nemtseva, and B.I. Ishanov centered on examining the intricate fortifications, architectural characteristics, and the findings.

¹⁹ <https://whc.unesco.org/en/list/603>

Picture from Google earth. (current view)

The first wall of the city. Western side. (Vyatkin. 1947)

V.L. Vyatkin and O.G. Bolshakov have provided in-depth analytical information about the Afrasiyob city in their books. Given that the majority of the Islamic pottery artifacts in the museum were discovered in Afrasiyob during the study, it can be

concluded that the development of ornamental themes was influenced by the history of this city.

Regarding the Samarkand Museum itself, a great deal of general information has been gathered and very few people have examined the displays. The book-album "[The Collection of the Samarkand State Museum-Reserve](#)" (XVIII volume in the series) "Cultural legacy of Uzbekistan in the world collections confirms that.

Decorative motifs.

To answer what kind of decoration types are used in these ceramics which has been presented are included in several articles and books of issues, such as *The art of Islamic pottery by Ernst J.Grube* and *Possible Sources for Some Motifs of Decoration on Islamic Ceramics by Fay Arrieh Frick.*. By the method of analyzing these data, it is determined that types of pottery products are divided in terms of raw materials and appearance. Also Vyatkin in his book *Afrasiyab* gave overall view about ancient city and its history in absolutely unique way. According to V.L. Vyatkin, the first glazed vessels of Samarkand came from abroad in the IV-VII centuries. According to I.A. Sukharev, as a result of the Arab invasion in Samarkand in the 20th of the VIII century Glazed ceramics appeared for the first time. At the *Afrosiyab* monument A.I. Terenojkin, who conducted archaeological research, Samarkand pottery of about the 8th century by the middle of the 19th century, further shared his insightful thoughts about glazed vessels and Samarkand.

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